

FORWARD Visual identity and promotional material

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Visual identity

During the first months of activity, the ITC created the project visual identity, including logo, roll-up banner, slides' template, and other relevant promotional material to be used in dissemination activities produced under WP8. All promotional materials is available in English and can be adapted to the project partners (ES, FR, PT), if necessary.

The FORWARD brand use manual is included as annex 1, including all the templates developed.

1 Logo

The ITC made a proposal for the selection of the Forward logo with 3 options. The partnership, through online voting, selected option 1.

	Logo 1	Logo 2	Logo 3
20 participantes	✓ 13	✓ 5	✓ 6

1.1 Logo proposals

Option 1: Stars, coloured in the blue of European Union flag, represent the union between 9 outermost regions. Waves in 3 colours (Same as OMR logo colours) represent the sea, as link between territories. The arrow represents the innovation and leadership that the project aims to achieve.

Option 2: It represents triangles as symbols of leadership and growing, and also as representation of islands territories. The union between the spots represents the link between different regions across the distance.

Option 3: It represents the light bulb as the symbol of the innovation and ideas. 9 stars symbolize the regions following an ascending spiral that represents the progress of territories across the R&D. Green and blue waves represent the sea as link between outermost regions.

Annex 1 FORWARD brand use manual

BRAND USE MANUAL

Complete branding creation from logotype
to communication tools and illustrations

Horizon Europe Programme
#Forwardh2020

Introduction

This manual consists of a guide for the correct use and application of the **FORWARD** and **European Union Emblem** corporate design elements and image.

Its goal is to communicate **FORWARD** brand effectively. It is part of the **WP8 – Dissemination and communication. Task 8.2 Visual identity, promotional material and project's branding.**

All the logos (project, programme, partners), manuals, templates, banners and promotional tools designs referenced in this manual are available in the **Google Drive directory** of the FORWARD project, folder '**Visual identity, templates and communication material**'.

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CORPORATE ELEMENTS

BRAND USE MANUAL

1.1 LOGO

The generic brand of the FORWARD project consists of logo, legend and symbol.

It is recommended to use the design (square or rectangular) that best adapt to the format where is displayed.

The **corporate logo** can be used in different forms in order to a correct adaptation to the format where is displayed.

If possible, it is recommended to use full colour logo (square or rectangular) instead of monochromatic shapes.

1.2 COLOURS

FORWARD has 4 corporate colours in its main logo.

It is recommended to use those colours and its chromatic variants in the designs of the project.

<p>HEX : #073e8e</p> <p>R 7 G 62 B 142 C 100 M 81 Y 11 K 1</p>	<p>HEX : #0090cf</p> <p>R 0 G 144 B 207 C 79 M 30 Y 0 K 0</p>
<p>HEX : #fed503</p> <p>R 254 G 213 B 3 C 1 M 15 Y 93 K</p>	<p>HEX : #179e40</p> <p>R 23 G 158 B 64 C 81 M 7 Y 96 K 0</p>

1.3 LOGO TYPOGRAPHY

The basic font for the logo of FORWARD project is the **TimeBurner**.

This typography and **Pt Sans** font can be used in headings, titles and subtitles.

TimeBurner Bold

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
123456789

TimeBurner Regular

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
123456789

Pt Sans Bold

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
123456789

1.4 TEXTS TYPOGRAPHY

Typography used for **FORWARD** texts is the **Pt Sans Bold or Regular**.

Pt Sans Bold

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
123456789

Pt Sans Regular

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
123456789

“

Lique reperuptus magnam idi blantur accum ilignia tectatem fuga. Nequam ent. As est auda sum, simporestem volupic imolesedis quo exped es aborecu lparume dolesentia veneculpa erum sinvendaes solores temporibus exeriasi sundam, ab incimus, aliteca boreprat vollati onempores audist exceatq uianihit magnam faccae laboribus et eostia venimporro magna dellendit ipsam untia dolorep eliquam nonsequos endi dolupic iaecte omnis pel incti temquas si doles sitese ommodist, que porepe volor arias volupti repeligni blanimi liquis alitatur mintiunt fugita ditatur ecumqui berspid eum illaccus ellant quiatus amendus.

”

EUROPEAN UNION EMBLEM

BRAND USE MANUAL

2.1 GENERAL RULES

All partners must take consideration of European Commission “Brand design manual” and display the Union Emblem in all communications of FORWARD project, according the rules explained on ‘Guidelines for beneficiaries and other third parties’.

The next points are some of the most important rules that must be followed :

- The minimum height of the EU emblem shall be 1 cm.
- The name of the European Union shall always be spelled out in full.
- The typeface to be used in conjunction with the EU emblem can be any of the following: Arial, Calibri, Garamond, Trebuchet, Tahoma, Verdana. Italic and underlined variations and the use of font effects are not allowed.
- The positioning of the text in relation to the EU emblem is not prescribed in any particular way but the text should not interfere with the emblem in any way.
- The font size used should be proportionate to the size of the emblem.
- The colour of the font should be reflex blue (same blue colour as the EU flag), black or white depending on the background.

2.2 EUROPEAN UNION EMBLEM

The European Union Emblem of FORWARD project. It is recommended to use the design (square or rectangular) that best adapt to the format where is displayed.

This project has received funding from European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 824550

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1 cm

BRAND FOR OR RESEARCH

BRAND USE MANUAL

3.1 OR RESEARCH BRAND

The **OR research brand** will be initially used by the **regional institutions** that **participate in FORWARD project**, both as partners or stakeholders, in their communication material such as websites, posters, leaflets, tailored info sheets on research topics/ activities of excellence in ORs, etc.

COMMUNICATION TOOLS

BRAND USE MANUAL

4.1 MAIN ROLL-UP

FORWARD has a **corporative Roll-Up** which should be displayed on all project events if does not exist a specific poster or roll-up for that event.

Generic

Specific

4.2 BANNERS AND OTHER DESIGN

Banners, social media covers, screen wallpapers, or any other resource can be created following the logo, colours, typography, and European Emblem rules explained in this manual.

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